
Chemical Analysis of Water Samples from the Degema, Abonnema and Billeaxis of Sombriero River, Niger Delta, Nigeria

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Abstract The Degema, Abonnema and Bille axis of the Sombriero River in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria were assessed for a period of three years during the dry season of January to March 2010, 2011 and 2012 for physicochemical parameters and heavy metal concentrations. The physicochemical parameters were analyzed using APHA standard methods while the heavy metals were determined with Atomic Absorption Spectroscopic method. Results obtained indicated that pH, Electrical conductivity, Chloride, Total Hardness, COD and BOD increased from 2010 to 2012; Turbidity, TSS, TDS and TOC decreased in 2011 but increased in the preceding year 2012 whereas M-Alkalinity, O-Phosphate and Nitrate increased in 2011 but decreased in the preceding year 2012. The heavy metal concentrations showed the following order: Na>K>Mg>Cr>Fe>Pb>Ni in the years under investigation but in 2010 (Mn>Cd>Cu>Zn); 2011 (Cd>Mn>Cu>Zn) and 2012 (Mn>Cd>Cu>Zn). These variations may be due to changes in the water and chemical compositions and therefore suitable for aquatic activities.

Keywords Chemical analysis, Sombriero River, Niger Delta, Degema, Abonnema, Bille

Introduction

The Sombriero River is one of the rivers that drain the western part of Rivers State. The river provides nursery and breeding grounds for a large variety of fish species [1] it is contained within the tropical rain forest although the lower reach is within the brackish mangrove zone.

The physicochemical characteristics of water are important parameters as they may directly or indirectly affect its quality and subsequently its suitability for the distribution and production of fish and other aquatic animals [2]. Also, variability of water quality influences the toxicity levels of heavy metals on estuarine organisms as it affects the physicochemical composition of the ecosystem [3].

Heavy metals occur naturally as ore deposits and are released into the aquatic environment through leaching or weathering [4-5]. Various human activities such as fishing, sand running, dredging public toilets, refuse dumps, run-offs into the river, mangrove cutting, logging of timbers and transportation may be potential sources of pollution to the environment [6]. Hence, the need for the chemical analysis of the Degema, Abonnema and Bille axis of the Sombriero river to be compared to previous studies within the study area.

Materials and Methods

Description of the Study Area

Sombriero River (Fig. 1) is located across six (6) Local Government Areas of Rivers State – Akuku-toro, Degema, Asari-toru, Abua-Odual, Ikwerre and Emohua between Latitude 4° 22' 47" N and Longitude 6° 52' 20" E. It is a distributary of the River Niger which drains into the Atlantic Ocean connected to other rivers via creeks in the

coastal area of Niger Delta [1]. The vegetation fringes the river at the left and right banks consisting of mangrove tress (*Rhizophora*, *avicennia* and *nypha fruticans*), arising from a characteristic muddy substrate that produces a foul odour.

Figure 1: Map of study area (Courtesy: Google map)

Sample Collection and Analysis

The water was sampled during the dry season months of February and March 2010, 2011 and 2012. Three sampling points for each location were 500m apart along the stretch of the Degema, Abonnema and Bille axis of the Sombriero River. The subsurface composite samples were obtained by sampling from the entire sampling stations. The sampling containers used were washed with detergent, rinsed with 1M Nitric acid after which they were severely washed with deionized water and finally with the sample solution before collection of samples for analysis. The samples were collected with a 2 Litres plastic hydro bios water sampler and transferred to clean 2Litres polyethylene containers with screw caps. Samples used for heavy metals were preserved by the addition of concentrated Nitric acid (4ml). All the samples were transported in an ice-chest to the laboratory and preserved in a refrigerator at 4 °C. The samples were analyzed within twenty-four hours of arrival. The physicochemical parameters investigated were pH measured with Orion Digital pH meter and Electrical Conductivity determined with Thermo Orion conductivity meter and M-alkalinity, Turbidity, Total Suspended Solids (TSS), Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Chloride, Ortho-Phosphate, Soluble Silica, Nitrate, Total hardness, Calcium hardness, Magnesium hardness, Total Organic Carbon (TOC), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) and Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD) analysed with standard methods for examination of water and wastewater (APHA 2000). Aliquot samples for heavy metal of Fe, Zn, Cd, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, Mn, Mg, Na and K were concentrated and analyzed with Perkin Elmer A Analyst 200 AAS.

Results and Discussion

The results of the physicochemical parameter and heavy metals of the Sombriero river of Degema, Abonnema and Bille axis presented in Tables 1-6 respectively. Considering Tables 1-3, the pH measurements were near neutral to neutral. The lowest mean value was in 2010 and highest mean value in 2012. According to Abowei [7], the pH higher than 7.0 but lower than 8.5 is ideal for biological productivity while pH lower than 4 is detrimental to aquatic life. Water with pH values of 6.5 to 9.0 are considered best for fish production [8-9]. Hence, Sombriero river axis under investigation was good for aquatic activities. The Electrical Conductivity varies averagely from 13.94ms/cm by Degema in 2010 to 18.79ms/cm by Bille in 2012. Natural waters have conductivity of 20-1500 μ S/cm [7]. However, the Sombriero river axis analysed fell below the range (Figure 2a). This may be attributed to the changes in water composition due to rainfall, evaporation, precipitation and/or other weather factors. The relatively uniform conductivity observed in the three locations may be due to wave, wind and tidal mixtures. The water samples were clear; hence the turbidity, Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) and Total Suspended solids (TSS) were also low. The

Chloride ions present in the samples were very high. Powell *et al* [10]; Wuenschel *et al* [11], Ansa, [12] and Jamabo [13] reported that the chloride concentration level is considerably higher during the dry season when sea water penetrates far up the rivers than in rainy season when rain water and flood from the Niger and Benue rivers drive the salt water back towards the sea. They also concluded that, the Bonny River has high salinity (chloride) penetration from the Atlantic Ocean which salinity fluctuates with the season and tide. Hence, salinity (chloride) is a major driving force that affects the density of growth of aquatic organisms' population in the mangrove swamp. This may be the reason why the Sombriero River water samples collected in the dry season was as high as 4802, 5771 and 6237 for 2010, 2011 and 2012 respectively (Figure 2c).

The waters (2010, 2011 and 2012) were considered hard since the least and highest values were 1480 and 1875 respectively. There was a steady increase of Total Hardness from 2010-2012. This may be attributed to the Calcium, Sodium, Potassium and Magnesium cations present in the water. The Total Organic Carbon (TOC) in the water was 1.71mg/L (2010) minimum and 6.06 mg/L (2012) maximum. In 2010, the TOC values were 0.06, 1.75 and 10.79 at Degema, Abonnema and Bille respectively. The high TOC in Bille may be due to the crude oil exploration activities within that axis. In 2011, the TOC values were within the range of 1.17 to 1.69 but increased in 2012 to 5.52mg/L to 6.48mg/L. However the year, 2012, the activities of illegal oil bunkering had started rearing its ugly head which the Sombriero River being used as the ferrying axis. On the other hand, in 2010, the COD was 447ppm and BOD was 89ppm. While 2011, COD was 643ppm and BOD 129ppm. In 2012, COD 643ppm and BOD 129ppm (Figure 2b). The increase may be due to human activities and drains depositing waste into the river during the rainy season.

Table 1: Physicochemical parameters of Sombriero River (Bille, Abonnema & Degema axis) in 2010

Parameter (ppm)	Sombriero by Degema	Sombriero by Abonnema	Sombriero by Bille	Mean \pm std. dev
pH	6.8	6.8	6.8	6.8 \pm 0.00
E.C (μ S/cm)	13.94	14.01	13.98	13.98 \pm 0.03
Alkalinity	39.00	40.00	40.00	39.67 \pm 0.57
Turbidity (NTU)	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.33 \pm 0.57
TSS (mg/L)	2.00	4.00	3.00	3.00 \pm 1.00
TDS	5.00	4.00	3.00	4.00 \pm 1.00
Chloride	4779.06	4824.10	4801.55	4801.57 \pm 22.52
O-PO ₄ ³⁻	0.52	0.50	0.44	0.49 \pm 0.04
Total Hardness	1485	1510	1445	1480 \pm 32.78
TOC	0.60	1.75	2.79	1.71 \pm 1.09
COD	452	440	448	446.67 \pm 6.11
BOD	90	88	90	89.33 \pm 1.22
Nitrite	80	400	320	266.67 \pm 166.53

Table 2: Physicochemical parameters of Sombriero River (Bille, Abonnema & Degema axis) in 2011

Parameter (ppm)	Sombriero by Degema	Sombriero by Abonnema	Sombriero by Bille	Mean \pm std. dev
pH	7.0	7.1	7.1	7.1 \pm 0.05
E.C (μ S/cm)	17.26	17.11	17.14	17.17 \pm 0.07
Alkalinity	44.00	51.00	53.00	49.33 \pm 4.72
Turbidity (NTU)	2.00	1.00	1.00	1.33 \pm 0.57
TSS (mg/L)	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00 \pm 0.00
TDS	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.33 \pm 0.57
Chloride	5815.97	5770.88	5725.80	5770.88 \pm 45.08
O-PO ₄ ³⁻	0.53	0.55	0.52	0.53 \pm 0.01
Total Hardness	1690	1780	1660	1710 \pm 62.44
TOC	1.30	1.17	1.69	1.39 \pm 0.27
COD	625	620	685	643.33 \pm 36.17
BOD	125	123	138	128.67 \pm 8.14
Nitrite	4000	4000	3600	3866.67 \pm 230.94

Table 3: Physicochemical parameters of Sombriero River (Bille, Abonnema & Degema axis) in 2012

Parameter (ppm)	Sombriero by Degema	Sombriero by Abonnema	Sombriero by Bille	Mean \pm std. dev
pH	7.2	7.2	7.3	7.2 \pm 0.05
E.C (μ S/cm)	18.72	18.20	18.79	18.57 \pm 0.32
Alkalinity	46.00	45.00	45.50	45.50 \pm 0.5
Turbidity (NTU)	2.00	3.00	2.00	2.33 \pm 0.57
TSS (mg/L)	3.00	2.00	3.00	2.67 \pm 0.57
TDS	2.00	2.00	1.00	1.67 \pm 0.57
Chloride	6279.95	6236.64	6193.33	6236.64 \pm 43.31
O-PO ₄ ³⁻	0.21	0.20	0.22	0.21 \pm 0.01
Total Hardness	1842	1960	1823	1875.07 \pm 74.20
TOC	6.48	5.52	6.18	6.06 \pm 0.49
COD	656	678	595	643 \pm 43.00
BOD	131	136	119	128.67 \pm 8.73
Nitrite	3800	3600	3500	3633.33 \pm 152.75

Table 4: Heavy metal parameters of Sombriero River (Bille, Abonnema & Degema axis) in 2010

Heavy metal (ppm)	Sombriero by Degema	Sombriero by Abonnema	Sombriero by Bille	Mean \pm std. dev
Fe	0.22	0.43	0.24	0.30 \pm 0.11
Zn	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02 \pm 0.01
Cu	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02 \pm 0.01
Cr	0.86	0.90	0.82	0.86 \pm 0.04
Cd	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02 \pm 0.01
Ni	0.08	0.05	0.06	0.06 \pm 0.02
Pb	0.10	0.05	0.10	0.08 \pm 0.03
Mn	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.04 \pm 0.01
Mg	3.17	3.22	3.16	3.18 \pm 0.03
Na	29.10	29.09	29.07	29.09 \pm 0.02
K	7.78	7.78	7.79	7.78 \pm 0.01

Table 5: Heavy metal parameters of Sombriero River (Bille, Abonnema & Degema axis) in 2011

Heavy metal (ppm)	Sombriero by Degema	Sombriero by Abonnema	Sombriero by Bille	Mean \pm std. dev
Fe	0.15	0.12	0.12	0.13 \pm 0.12
Zn	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01 \pm 0.01
Cu	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01 \pm 0.01
Cr	0.78	0.76	0.80	0.78 \pm 0.04
Cd	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.04 \pm 0.01
Ni	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.07 \pm 0.02
Pb	0.10	0.05	0.10	0.08 \pm 0.03
Mn	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02 \pm 0.01
Mg	3.15	3.19	3.19	3.18 \pm 0.03
Na	28.82	29.10	29.00	28.97 \pm 0.02
K	7.52	7.54	7.55	7.54 \pm 0.01

Table 6: Heavy metal parameters of Sombriero River (Bille, Abonnema & Degema axis) in 2012

Heavy metal (ppm)	Sombriero by Degema	Sombriero by Abonnema	Sombriero by Bille	Mean \pm std. dev
Fe	0.05	0.11	0.05	0.07 \pm 0.03
Zn	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02 \pm 0.00
Cu	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02 \pm 0.00
Cr	0.98	0.92	0.97	0.96 \pm 0.03

Cd	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02 ± 0.00
Ni	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.07 ± 0.02
Pb	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06 ± 0.00
Mn	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.02 ± 0.01
Mg	3.21	3.19	3.18	3.19 ± 0.02
Na	30.11	30.24	30.30	30.22 ± 0.09
K	7.66	7.68	7.71	7.68 ± 0.03

Figure 2 (a), (b) and (c): Physicochemical parameters in Sombriero river of Degema, Abonnema and Bille axis

Figure 3 (a), (b) and (c): Heavy metals in Sombriero river of Degema, Abonnema and Bille axis in 2010, 2011 and 2012

Tables 4-6 showed the level of heavy metals in the Degema, Abonnema and Bille axis of Sombriero River are low except for the alkali and alkaline earth metals (Mg, Na, K) which were considerably high.

In 2010, **Na>K>Mg>Cr>Fe>Pb>Mn>(Cd/Cu/Zn)**

In 2011, **Na>K>Mg>Cr>Fe>Pb>Ni>Cd>Mn>(Cu/Zn)**

In 2012, **Na>K>Mg>Cr>(Fe/Ni)>Pb>(Mn/Cd/Cu/Zn)**

The heavy metals present in the river in concentration levels (Na, K, Mg and Fe) were expected except for Cr, Ni, Pb, Mn and Cd with trace amounts which is of urgent concern because of bioaccumulation and biomagnification processes to aquatic life. Hence, the control of waste discharge from market stalls, slaughter houses, sewage discharges into the river should be checked especially during the dry season.

Conclusion

The Sombriero river axis under review is suitable for aquatic activities as it plays a major role in the distribution of fish. The level of some heavy metals detected should be checked and the annual increase of organic compounds observed should be monitored as well. Also, the activities of the illegal refining processes sprouting up should be discouraged so as to keep our ecosystem intact.

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